

INTERNALIZATION OF PANCASILA VALUES IN FOSTERING THE CHARACTER OF GRADE 11 BINA DHARMA STUDENTS

Debora Putriani Br Nainggolan¹, Leory Yunistia Jasmine², Maulia Depriya Kembara³

nainggolan.putri1254@gmail.com¹, oikprambudi@gmail.com², maulia@upi.edu³

Universitas Negeri Medan

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to find out what is the role of Pancasila values in the character development of Bina Dharma XI students. The method used is qualitative research. The data collection technique was done through triangulation which is a combination of observation, interview, and documentation. The results obtained through the research are that although 11th grade students understand the values of Pancasila, they are still passive in practicing Pancasila values. In education, Pancasila values can be incorporated into school subjects through practices that teachers can apply in learning activities.

Keywords: Pancasila values, Character Education

INTRODUCTION

Pancasila is a guide to life, thought and behavior of various tribes, nations, religions and races in Indonesia (Ardhani et al., 2022). The good or bad of an attitude or action is based on the values contained in the Pancasila of Indonesian society. The main purpose of Pancasila is the principle or rule of organizing the life of the nation and state.

The legacy of Indonesian educators must be understood and applied in everyday life, so that it is not lost. If you understand this and indeed all the diversity that exists in Indonesia is not divisive. In addition, the application of Pancasila also supports the realization of the character of Indonesian human resources.

The values contained in Pancasila are taken from norms, values, rules and policies that develop in Indonesian society (Sulistyarini et al., 2020). The life of the Indonesian nation requires the realization of the noble values contained in Pancasila which reflect the original personality of the Indonesian people. The values, norms, and ethics contained in Pancasila have indeed become a very complete and rounded unity and can be integrated into the personality of every Indonesian citizen to shape attitudes, mindsets, and actions and become a guideline for Indonesian society. These values become the understanding and paradigm of character education in Indonesia. The introduction of Pancasila values should remain in the soul of all Indonesian citizens so that the hopes and noble goals of the Indonesian nation are realized and the struggle of our predecessors to achieve independence from colonizers and colonizers is not in vain. formulate Pancasila according to the conscience of the community, because it sees that the Indonesian nation has differences in culture, language, ethnicity, customs, local wisdom and religion, so that one and the other are not divided so that the Indonesian nation becomes a unified whole (Zaman et al., 2022).

However, most Indonesians consider Pancasila only as the basis of state/ideology without considering the purpose and benefits of life (Erlina, 2019). Without humans understanding its values, the meaning contained in Pancasila is very helpful and useful. Many certain deviations / mistakes are actually caused by the non-implementation of the values contained in Pancasila. Therefore, the importance of understanding Pancasila is not only understanding, but also practicing and applying the values contained in Pancasila as

the essence of education. Character education that aims to implement the mandate of Pancasila and the preamble of the 1945 Constitution is based on the current reality in educational institutions. With behavior that is not in accordance with the current character of the Indonesian nation. The cultivation of good character should not only include good knowledge (moral knowledge), but also good feelings or rejection of goodness (moral feeling) and good behavior (moral action).

Character education emphasizes habits that are consistently practiced according to the values of Pancasila. Pancasila education in everyday life can have a good influence on society so that people follow and adhere to the values of Pancasila, because the values contained in Pancasila have many meanings in everyday life both in religion, opinion, and others. Pancasila as a state ideology has an important role in creating the direction and foundation of social and national life in Indonesia. The purpose of Pancasila as a guide to life is also the formation of national character and national personality. Where in the formation of the nation's character, the values of Pancasila have a great influence on the quality of human resources (HR), as stated by the Minister of Education and Culture since the beginning, or often referred to as the founders. realized that to realize these ideals, Indonesia is not just a country that must be built, but also a nation. Thus, in the context of character building, Pancasila must be taken seriously as the main guideline and source of nation building, considering that Pancasila is a reflection of the nation, so it is appropriate for Indonesian citizens to apply the values of Pancasila in life, one of the most important ways is through the world of education (Mifdal Zusron Affaqi, 2016).

Education has an important role as an educator of the nation's children: intelligence is not just intelligence, but total intelligence that focuses on intelligence, able to develop potential within. This is in line with the objectives of Indonesian national education as stated in the preamble of the 1945 Constitution. In addition, the formulation of the objectives of national education also contains noble morals that prove that Indonesia raises the identity of its people to be able to behave well according to existing standards. Intelligent nature becomes the foundation of thinking so that humans can live their lives well, harmoniously, and prosperously, which not only benefits themselves but also others. However, the current reality is that Indonesian society is experiencing a moral crisis due to a lack of intelligent thinking, one of which is in the school environment. Common problems in the school environment are violence between students and other students (bullying), independence, indifference, deep-rooted dishonesty, loss of respect for parents, teachers and other problems.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative research using descriptive methods. Sugiyono explained, qualitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of post-positivism and interpretative, and is used to study the state of natural objects, with the researcher as the main instrument. Data collection techniques through triangulation, namely combining observation, interviews, and documentation. The data obtained is usually qualitative. Data analysis is done inductively or qualitatively. Meanwhile, the results of qualitative research are understanding meaning, understanding specificity, constructing phenomena, and finding hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2017: 9). To achieve good research results, researchers must have comprehensive knowledge of information and data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Character education is a very difficult thing to understand the quality of a nation,

this is related to the moral crisis that has occurred recently. With the deteriorating quality of morals and morality, especially among students, schools are the right place for character education. Schools must be able to encourage and develop good values to shape student character. Because education does not only function as a place to develop intellectual abilities, but also functions as a shaper of character, character and personality of students. In this regard, a person's character is essentially formed along with the stages of age development, character can be influenced by various aspects of the environment, ranging from the family environment, society to the environment where children receive information every day, namely school (Bahrudin, 2019). To know that character can develop requires guidance and direction from students from all aspects, one of which is school. Pancasila is the foundation that must be applied in the lives of students in realizing the character of students. Pancasila is not only the foundation of the state, but also the foundation of character building. Pancasila has values that can make the nature of its citizens become more religious, noble, tolerant, and others. In this regard, the form of Pancasila is intended as a way of thinking and acting for every citizen. In realizing the character of elementary school students, Pancasila is the foundation that must be applied in student life. Pancasila is not only the foundation of the state, but also the foundation of character building. By incorporating Pancasila values into the education curriculum, students can learn about the importance of national identity, national values and Indonesia's cultural diversity. This helps to create a generation that has a high awareness of the importance of maintaining national identity and becoming responsible citizens. Pancasila has values that can shape the character of its citizens to be more religious, noble, tolerant, etc. In this regard, Pancasila character is intended as a way of thinking and acting of every citizen. In this regard, the character of Pancasila is intended as a way of thinking and acting of every citizen.

A. Values Contained In Pancasila

1. The Value Of Divinity (Religion)

Believing and fearing God Almighty in accordance with religion and belief is in line with the principles of just and civilized humanity. This noble value underlies the harmony of life in society, nation and state. Religious values are values related to a person's attachment to something he considers sacred, holy, great and noble. Understanding divinity as a guide to life means creating a pious society, namely building an Indonesian society that has the soul and spirit to achieve God's pleasure in every good deed. From the point of view of religion and ethics, a state founded on God Almighty is a state that guarantees the freedom of every citizen to embrace religion and worship according to their respective religions and beliefs.

2. Humanity (Morality)

Every citizen recognizes the principle of the unity of the Indonesian nation, the equality of degrees, rights and responsibilities of fellow human beings. By emphasizing equality of status, rights and responsibilities, all citizens can jointly safeguard and maintain dynamic coherence and lead to lasting stability. This awareness is the spirit of building the life of society and the universe to achieve happiness through long-term efforts, and can be realized in the form of a harmonious view of life, full of tolerance and peace (Nurgiansah and Al Muchtar, 2018).

3. Indonesian Unity (Nationality)

Every citizen prioritizes unity, integrity, national and state interests and security over personal and group interests. This attitude creates readiness and willingness to sacrifice for the sake of the people and the nation. A positive attitude is based on a sense of patriotism

and love for the country (nationalism).

4. Value Of Democracy Led By Wisdom In Deliberation/Representation

Every citizen or community member has the same position, rights and responsibilities. The same position is used consciously, by always considering first the interests of the state and society. In addition, as citizens, we must always prioritize reflection in order to reach an understanding in solving common problems.

5. Consultation And Representation

The basis of society is the promotion of mutual respect and fairness towards others. We should avoid frivolous attitudes, extravagant lifestyles or actions that are detrimental to the common good. It is important to try and appreciate the work of others to develop an attitude of coherence. In the event of a national crisis, there are serious threats to the survival of the nation and state, as well as the actions of groups that lead to the collapse of the nation, but Pancasila is always a common guide, and the ideology of the nation.

B. Application Of Pancasila Values In Character Education

Character education is the realization of the mandate contained in Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. In addition, character education is also part of Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Based on this, it can be seen that character education is a very important education according to the mandate of Pancasila, and according to Ki Hajar Dewantara, the national education system / education law is a conscious effort to develop all aspects of humanity. knowledge, attitudes, values and skills. So people who behave badly such as lying and being cruel can be said to have bad morals, while people who behave well such as helping people have noble morals.

The purpose of national culture and character education is to prepare students to become better citizens, citizens who have the ability, willingness and values of Pancasila to be applied in their lives as citizens (Puskur, 2010: 8). The values of character education consist of: Religion: attitudes and behaviors that are obedient in applying the teachings of the religion they adhere to, tolerant of the worship of other religions and living in

harmony with followers of other religions. Integrity: behavior based on efforts to become a person who can always be trusted in words, actions, and work.

In addition, (Erna Octavia, 2017: 116) says that the character of individuals who are loaded with the values of the Pancasila precepts consists of two sources, namely characters born from the training of the heart and mind. The characteristics of the heart include honesty, faith and piety, justice, order, reliability, obedience to rules, responsibility, empathy, courage to take risks, never give up, willing to sacrifice and patriotism. Characters born from thinking are intelligent, critical, creative, innovative, curious, useful and wise.

From this it can be concluded that character education as a reflection of oneself is an important and main thing in terms of students' personalities, especially in the early stages of primary classes. With the implementation of character education, it is hoped that students can shape the character of the nation in accordance with the principles and noble values that guide daily behavior, and with this character education is also a green light to prevent the crisis of Indonesian civilization, and the emerging morality.

CONCLUSIONS

Pancasila has noble values that can be used as guidelines for life in the nation and state. The planting and application of Pancasila values is very important and necessary in shaping the personality of the nation's generation with character so that generations can appreciate and live in peace and morally and be able to compete in all fields. And the

application of character education must be instilled early so that later the value of Pancasila will be inherent in the character and personality of each individual in society in order to always create a peaceful Indonesian nation. In education, Pancasila values can be integrated with existing subjects in schools through habituation that teachers can apply in their learning activities. Because Pancasila is the initial foundation in building a smart, creative and noble personal character.

LITERATURE

- Affaqi, m. Z. (2016). Melihat sejarah nasionalisme Indonesia untuk memupuk sikap kebangsaan generasi muda. *Jurnal Civics: Media Kajian Kewarganegaraan*, 13(2), 209-216.
- Ardhani, M. D. (2022). Implementasi Nilai nilai Pancasila dalam kehidupan sehari-hari. *Jurnal Gema Keadilan*.
- Bahrudin, F. A. (2019). Implementasi Kompetensi Mata Kuliah Pendidikan. *Pro Patria: Jurnal Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan, Hukum, Sosial, Dan Politik*, 2(2), 184-200.
- Erlina, t. (2019). Membangun Karakter Ke-Indonesiaan Pancasila melalui Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan Di Era Global. *FACTUM: Jurnal Sejarah Dan Pendidikan Sejarah*, 8(2), 153-162. doi:<https://doi.org/10.17509/factum.v8i2.21612>
- Erna, O. (2017). Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter Berbasis Pancasila Untuk Membentuk Mahasiswa Prodi Ppkn Menjadi Warga Negara yang Baik dan Cerdas. *Sosial Horizon: Jurnal Pendidikan Sosial*, 4. (1), 111-124.
- HU Billah, M. Y. (2023). Kesadaran Berpancasila Dalam Mempertahankan Identitas Nasional. *Jurnal Bintang Pendidikan Indonesia*, Vol 1 No 2.
- Sulistyarini, R. R. (2020). Pancasila Character Education in Teaching Materials to Develop College Students' Civic Disposition. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 418(Acec 2019), 325–330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200320.063>
- Zaman, M. B. (2022). Harmonisasi Pendidikan Islam dan Negara: Pengarustamaan Nilai-nilai Pancasila dalam Orientasi Pendidikan Pesantren di Indonesia. *Jurnal Tarbawi Stai Al Fithrah*, 10(2), 139–1644.